

Effects of Thermal Fluctuations on the Hydroxylation and Reduction of Ceria Surfaces by Molecular H₂

Fabio R Negreiros, Matteo Farnesi Camellone, and Stefano Fabris*

CNR-IOM DEMOCRITOS, Istituto Officina dei Materiali, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche and SISSA Scuola Internazionale di Studi Superiori Avanzati, Via Bonomea 265, I-34136, Trieste, Italy.

E-mail: fabris@sissa.it

Abstract

The hydroxylation of oxide surfaces driven by molecular H₂ dissociation plays a central role in a wide range of catalytic redox reactions. The high reducibility and oxygen storage capacity of ceria (CeO₂) surfaces account for its extensive use as active catalyst support in these redox reactions. By means of ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations, we investigate the hydroxylation and reduction of ceria surfaces and demonstrate the so-far unrecognized effects of atomic thermal fluctuations into the mechanism and kinetics of H₂ dissociation. The reaction free-energy hypersurface is sampled and mapped at finite temperature by combining Hubbard-U density functional theory (DFT+U), ab-initio molecular dynamics, metadynamics, and umbrella sampling methods. Our molecular dynamics simulations show that the explicit inclusion of thermal fluctuations into the reaction thermodynamics alters the mechanism of H₂ dissociation, changes the nature of the rate-limiting transition state, and decreases the activation temperatures by more than 25%. The results are discussed in the context of kinetic measurements

*To whom correspondence should be addressed

and provide novel insight into the hydroxylation and reduction steps that control the catalytic activity and selectivity of ceria surfaces.

Introduction

The dissociation of molecular hydrogen at oxide surfaces and the formation of surface hydroxyls are fundamental precursor steps in hydrogenation catalysis¹ for the industrial synthesis of chemical products and for technological applications such as fuel cells² or emission control.³ Ceria (CeO_2) surfaces play a central role in these contexts since they are known to efficiently promote hydrogenation reactions, often in conjunction with supported or dispersed metals.³ A selection of applications include the catalytic hydrogenation of CO_2 (reverse water-gas shift),⁴ dehydration of alcohols and other functional groups, (photo)-catalytic water splitting, and redox reactions in general.⁵ The high reducibility of ceria plays a key role in all these catalytic reactions and hydrogen activation is considered to be the rate-limiting step in many conversion reactions.¹

Due to their importance, ceria hydrogenation and reduction have been the subject of many scientific studies.³ Exposure to molecular H_2 is known to reduce and hydrogenate pure ceria surfaces.^{3,6,7} In the context of our study, it is important to distinguish irreversible reduction, which leads to water desorption via the formation of O vacancies and Ce^{3+} ions, from reversible reduction, which leads to surface hydroxylation and formation of Ce^{3+} ions.^{8,9} The measured activation temperatures for these reductions are very different. Magnetic susceptibility and X-ray photoemission measurements show that reversible reduction begins at $T \approx 470$ K, irrespective of the initial surface area of the ceria.^{9,10} Instead, temperature programmed reduction show that irreversible reduction requires temperatures higher than 600 K, with strong variations depending on textural and morphological properties.⁸

The atomistic details of the reduction mechanism, the nature of the rate-limiting step and the related activation energy governing the reaction kinetics remains however not fully

established. Fundamental insight into these issues can be obtained by sampling the reaction free-energy hypersurface at finite T , so as to identify the transition state in the minimum energy path (MEP) and the related activation energy, which is the subject of the present Letter.

A large majority of computational studies model reaction thermodynamics and kinetics on the basis of static calculations performed at $T=0$ K.¹¹ By following this approach, two recent works combined density functional theory (DFT+U) calculations with the Nudged Elastic Band¹² method to identify the minimum energy paths for H_2 dissociation on the $CeO_2(111)$ surface.^{13,14} These works predict that the reaction proceeds via a heterolytic dissociation mechanism that involves the transfer of a H atom to a surface O atom, the formation of two surface OH groups, and the reduction of two Ce^{4+} ions to Ce^{3+} . The calculated activation energies for this reversible reduction are 1.0¹³ and 1.1 eV,¹⁴ while the rate limiting step would be determined by the diffusion of the H atom from a Ce to an O surface site.

Atomic thermal fluctuations can indeed be neglected in many cases but they can also have important effects on the reaction mechanism and kinetics of H_2 dissociation.¹⁵ Including these terms into the calculations is challenging since it requires exploring the reaction free energy rather than the potential energy surface. However, reactions involving large displacements and diffusion of H atoms are known to be particularly affected by temperature effects because of enhanced anharmonic thermal fluctuations, fast proton chains and tunneling effects, which can reduce the H_2 dissociation barrier by as much as 0.3 eV.¹⁶ There are so far only few computational studies exploring the reactivity of ceria-based materials at finite temperature.¹⁷

We demonstrate here that ceria hydroxylation by H_2 is guided by entropic effects, which govern the reaction mechanisms, the rate-limiting step and activation energy. Density functional theory (DFT+U) and ab-initio Car-Parrinello molecular dynamics calculations combined with metadynamics and umbrella sampling methods allow to determine the reaction

free energy at finite temperatures without biases on final states and mechanisms, thus going beyond the usual $T=0\text{K}$ approximation in computational catalysis. By explicitly including entropic terms in the simulations we quantify their effects on the reaction thermodynamics and demonstrate how ceria hydroxylation by molecular H_2 is controlled by surface thermal fluctuations.

Methods

Computational details

Electronic-Structure Simulations.

All the calculations were performed in the frame work of density-functional theory (DFT) and employed periodic boundary conditions, plane waves basis sets and pseudopotentials. The calculations were spin polarized and employed the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE)¹⁸ exchange-correlation functional together with ultrasoft pseudopotentials. It is by now well established that the simulation of CeO_2 -based materials requires going beyond the standard functional and that the addition of a Hubbard U term to the Kohn Sham functional (DFT+ U) provides a reliable approach for these materials.¹⁹⁻²² We use the DFT+ U method as implemented by Cococcioni and de Gironcoli²³ and set the value of the parameter U to 4.5 eV following our previous works,²⁴⁻²⁸ and in line with the values used by the current literature.²² All calculations were performed with the Quantum Espresso (QE) package.²⁹

In the ab-initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations, the electronic wave function and density were described with a plane waves basis set that was limited by the energy cut offs of 25 Ry and 200 Ry, respectively, while the $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface was modeled by using 2x2 and 3x3 super cells with two O-Ce-O trilayers (one active plus one frozen) and with 12 Å of empty space between the slabs. The Brillouin zone was sampled at the Gamma point. These cut off values and supercell sizes are somewhat smaller than those used in

previous studies. This is due to the high computational cost of the present calculations with respect to standard total energy calculations or structural optimizations. In order to check the accuracy of this set up used in the AIMD, the relevant configurations for the T=0K minimum-energy path obtained with static calculations (see below) were also performed with a higher accuracy level, i.e., three O-Ce-O trilayers, 40/320 Ryd. of cutoff, 3x3 cell and 15Å of empty space. Differences of no more than 0.1eV/0.01Å for the energy differences and bond lengths were obtained. (additional details in SI)

Figure 1: Definitions of the collective variables (CVs) used to sample the free energy hypersurface.

Modeling the Reaction Thermodynamics.

The reaction thermodynamics in the potential energy, i.e. at T=0 K, were computed using the Climbing Image Nudged Elastic Band (CI-NEB) algorithm¹² using a Broyden scheme as implemented in the QE package. The reaction path was sampled with 6-8 intermediate images. **The robustness of the minimum energy path (MEP) resulting from the CI-NEB calculations was checked by starting them from several different initial paths, which all led to the same T=0K MEP.**

The reaction free-energy was studied with metadynamics and umbrella sampling techniques coupled to AIMD. We used two collective variables (CV) to sample the reaction free energy: i) the H-H distance $CV^{H-H} = d(H_a - H_b)$ and ii) the sum of the two shortest O-H distances between the molecule and two surface O atoms: $CV^{O-H} = d(O_a - H_a) + d(O_b - H_b)$ (see atoms labels in the inset of Fig. 1). Calculations with different CVs led to the same

result reported below (additional details in SI) hence we limit the analysis of the free energy to its projection on the subspace spanned by the two CV^{H-H} and CV^{O-H} variables.

All metadynamics simulations were carried out employing the efficient Car-Parrinello (CP) propagation method within the QE and PLUMED³⁰ software packages. A fictitious mass of 400 a.u. was used for the electronic degrees of freedom, and the nuclear mass of deuterium was used for all H atoms, thus allowing a time step of 5 a.u. (0.111 fs). The time-dependent biasing potential in our metadynamics simulations was build up by Gaussian functions with a height of 0.008 Ry and width of 0.1 Ry along the dynamics of the CVs. New biasing functions were added after 30 AIMD steps. The NVT ensemble has been established in all AIMD simulations using a thermostat temperature of $T = 350$ K. The temperature of both the electronic and nuclear degrees of freedom were controlled with independent thermostats by using **Nosé-Hoover** chains. **Also in the metadynamics simulations**, the $CeO_2(111)$ surface was modeled by using a 3x3 cell with two O-Ce-O trilayers (one active plus one frozen) and with 12 Å of empty space between replicated cells.

The umbrella sampling calculations involved about 500 AIMD runs of a total of **2.0ns**. These calculations sampled the free-energy subspace spanned by the two CVs in the following intervals: $0.7\text{Å} < CV^{H-H} < 4.0\text{Å}$ and $1.5\text{Å} < CV^{O-H} < 5.3\text{Å}$. The AIMD simulations were performed with a nose-thermostat at target temperatures of 150K/350K and a time step of 1fs. The free energy surface was constructed using the weighted histogram analysis method implemented in the WHAM package³¹ and the integration was performed in a box of about $0.05 \times 0.10\text{Å}$ for the $CV^{H-H} \times CV^{O-H}$ collective variables, respectively, discarding the initial 0.5ps of the run. **Additional details on the parameters of the MD simulations, on the convergency and error bars of the free-energy map obtained with the umbrella sampling simulations, and on the chosen CVs are included in the SI.**

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Potential Energy Surface: T=0 K.

Before assessing the free energy of hydrogen dissociation at ceria surfaces we establish and set as a baseline the corresponding minimum-energy reaction path in the potential energy, i.e., at T=0 K. Energies are referred to the initial state (IS) defined as a H₂ molecule in the gas phase and a stoichiometric CeO₂(111) surface, which is modeled by a 9-atom thick (3x3) supercell. We take as the final state (FS) two neighboring OH surface groups that result from the two H atoms of the H₂ molecule binding to the O-terminated ceria surface. The energy of this FS is 2.50 eV lower than the IS. The reaction is known to reduce the ceria surface and indeed the simulations of this FS predict the localisation of one electron on a Ce site below each surface OH group.

Table 1: Reaction energetics for the homolytic and heterolytic H₂ dissociations calculated with the CI-NEB method at T=0 K.

	homolytic			heterolytic				
	IS	TS	FS	IS	TS1	MS1	TS2	FS
This work	0.00	1.40	-2.50	0.00	0.72	0.70	0.99	-2.50
Fernandez-Torre <i>et al</i> ¹³	0.00	–	-2.34	0.00	0.77	0.77	0.99	-2.34
Garcia-Melchor <i>et al</i> ¹⁴	0.00	1.21	-2.40	0.00	0.85	0.75	1.08	-2.40

Our CI-NEB calculations identify two different reaction paths corresponding to homolytic and heterolytic H₂ surface dissociations, having activation energies of 1.40 and 0.97 eV, respectively (Table 1). These results are in good agreement with previous studies reporting 1.21¹⁴ eV and 1.08¹⁴-0.99 eV¹³ for the heterolytic and homolytic dissociations, respectively, obtained with the same DFT+U level of theory. A previous work also demonstrated that the inclusion of dispersion terms into these DFT calculation does not affect the binding energies substantially, reporting a binding increase of ≈ 50 meV only.¹³ We therefore neglect dispersion terms since their effects on the surface binding are not relevant at the temperatures considered in this work. Given the lower value of the activation energy for the heterolytic mechanism we analyze only this one in more detail.

Figure 2: Minimum energy path for the homolytic H₂ dissociation predicted by the CI-NEB calculations at 0K. Insets display the surface structure of relevant reaction configurations as well as selected inter atomic distances (in Å).

The total-energy profile along the minimum energy path (MEP) is displayed in Figure 2. The same Figure also reports the local atomistic structure and the values of the relevant bond lengths along the MEP. While decreasing the molecule-surface distance from the gas phase, the calculated energy profile displays a shallow (-0.05 eV) physisorption minimum in which molecular H_2 binds at the Ce site with H-Ce and H-O distances of 3.52 and 2.78 Å, respectively. This minimum is irrelevant for the surface chemistry described in the following.

The dissociation process initiates above a Ce site and proceeds by forming a bidentate Ce-H-H-O configuration (see panel A in Fig. 2). The binding to the surface O atom polarizes the H-H bond, which eventually breaks (transition state TS1), transferring to the ceria surface one electron that reduces one Ce atom (depicted in dark blue in Fig. 2). In this metastable state (MS), the two H atoms bind to a Ce and to an O atom, respectively, leading to the formation of a Ce^{3+} -H and a O-H surface groups. The MS is located in a very shallow minimum whose energy is 0.70 eV higher than that one of the IS. This is truly a relative minimum as demonstrated by its structural stability during MD calculations at T=20 K (details in SI). Note that this relative minimum becomes unstable and reaches the FS by rising the temperature to 50 K (SI).

The reaction proceeds to the FS with the migration of the H atom from the Ce^{3+} -H group to the neighboring O atom. This diffusion process requires to overcome a further energy barrier of 0.27 eV. The corresponding transition state (see TS2 in Fig. 2) is 0.99 eV above the IS and is actually the rate limiting step of the overall dissociation reaction. Very similar reaction paths and energetics (see Table 1) were obtained by the previous calculations.^{13,14}

Mapping the Reaction Free Energy Surface at Finite Temperature.

We now move from the reaction potential energy to the corresponding free energy. The goal is to determine the minimum-energy reaction path at finite T without assuming a specific mechanism or a final state, which are both usually enforced in the CI-NEB total-energy calculations. We employ DFT+U AIMD simulations coupled with the metadynamics

technique³² to sample the highly-dimensional reaction free energy at finite temperature in the space of a limited number of collective variables. This method allows to escape from the free-energy basin of the IS through the minimum-energy saddle point, thus predicting the reaction mechanism and the rate-limiting steps including explicitly the entropic effects. We sample the reaction free energy on a 2D subspace spanned by the CVs defined above (see Fig. 1). As a reference, the T=0K CI-NEB minimum-energy reaction path represented in the space of these CVs is reported in Fig.SX (gray squares).

We display in Fig. 3 the evolution of some relevant bond lengths (H-H, H-O, and H-Ce) during a section of the metadynamics run about the transition state. There are several events in which the gas-phase H₂ molecule interacts with the ceria surface (see dashed vertical lines). In all these cases (two examples are displayed in panels A and B) the H₂ molecule approaches the surface forming a monodentate bond with a terminating O atom. The dissociation event is evident from the quick transition in the H-H bond length, which increases from $\approx 0.75 \text{ \AA}$ (the equilibrium value in the gas phase) to $> 6 \text{ \AA}$. The breaking of the H-H bond is also evident from the increase of the molecular stretching frequency. These metadynamics simulations reveal that H₂ dissociation begins via a heterolytic mechanism but does not proceed along the same T=0K path identified with the static calculations. In particular, the Ce³⁺-H intermediate, which was stable and preceding the rate-limiting step in the T=0K simulations (MS in Fig. 2), is only briefly visited in the T=350K simulations (panel C in Fig. 3) and is therefore not a relevant intermediate in the finite-T reaction mechanism: The metadynamics simulations do not show the presence of a stable minimum about corresponding to the Ce³⁺-H configuration. In fact, the finite-T reaction mechanism predicted by these simulations show that the H₂ dissociation and the H diffusion are concerted, not stepwise as in the T=0K MEP: Upon increase of the intermolecular H-H bond length, both the H atoms proceed towards the closest O atoms, thus forming directly the two surface OH groups in the final state (panel D).

In summary, these ab-initio metadynamics simulations show that the fluctuations in

Figure 3: Analysis of the H-H, H-O, and H-Ce bond lengths during the metadynamics simulation. Snapshots of selected configurations (A-D) are reported in the top panels.

the surface atomic positions have an important impact on the reaction mechanism and destabilize the T=0K rate-limiting configurations. Reconstructing the free-energy profile along the finite-T path is however not possible with metadynamics, because of the long dynamics needed to sample the large IS basin. To reconstruct the free energy surface and to quantify the reaction activation energy we combine ab-initio MD simulations with the umbrella sampling method. This method allows for accelerating processes that occur on time scales that are beyond those that are accessible with the Car-Parrinello MD. The MD simulations were performed at T=150 K and T=350 K and the umbrella sampling was applied to the same collective variables used in the metadynamics calculations previously described, namely CV^{H-H} and CV^{O-H} (see Fig. 1). Both the metadynamics and umbrella sampling simulations therefore spanned and mapped the same two-dimensional subspace of the free-energy hypersurface.

The free energy surface (FES) reconstructed from the umbrella sampling MD simulations at T=350 K is displayed in Fig. 4. The IS and FS are located in the top-left and bottom-right corner of the plot, respectively. The minimum-energy path in this FES is marked with the solid black line and circles, while the gray line and squares marks the reaction path in the potential energy (T=0 K) represented in the space of these two CVs. It is evident that H₂ dissociation at T=350 K follows a different pathway (path 2 in Fig. 4) in the free-energy configuration space, with lower activation energies and intermediate states that significantly differ from the MEP in the PES predicted by the NEB simulations at T=0K, particularly in the second part of the reaction.

The reaction energetics along the MEP at these two temperatures are better compared in Fig. 5a), which displays them along the respective one-dimensional reaction coordinate, whose length has been normalised to 1. This comparison clearly shows that the free energy for the reaction at T= 350 K displays only one transition state (TS in path 2) whose activation barrier is the same of the first transition state (TS1 in path 1) in the T=0 K PES. When temperature activates ionic dynamics the reaction’s kinetics is determined by the actual

Figure 4: Free energy surface reconstructed from the umbrella sampling MD simulations at $T=350$ K. Black and gray symbols mark the minimum energy paths calculated at $T=350$ K and $T=0$ K, respectively.

Figure 5: a) One-dimensional representation of the reaction energetics along the minimum energy paths calculated at $T=0$ (path 1) and $T=350$ K (path 2). Total energy vs. free-energy profiles along b) path 1 and c) path 2. Entropic effects (TS) along the reaction paths 1 and 2. The yellow shaded area marks the region of the reaction path mostly affected by entropic effects.

breaking of the H-H bond, while in the static $T=0\text{K}$ calculations the rate is controlled by the proton diffusion on the ceria surface. We note that the calculated activation energy for proton diffusion between neighboring O-H surface groups is 1.8 eV ¹³. Temperature impacts on the second part of the dissociation, removing a high-energy plateau in the internal energy (see yellow-shaded area in Fig.5) and by opening a valley in the free energy landscape that leads directly from the TS saddle point to the FS basin (see Fig.4), avoiding the higher-energy TS1 saddle. The finite-T reaction mechanism (path 2) originates from a temperature-induced change in the topology of the energy surface, that destabilizes the $\text{Ce}^{3+} - \text{H}$ intermediate and opens a new MEP in the free-energy surface. We propose that this destabilization originates from the thermal motion of the surface O atoms, which assist the barrierless proton transfer required to hydroxylate ceria surfaces, i.e. forming OH groups at $\approx 4\text{ \AA}$ apart (panel D, Fig.3). Atomic thermal fluctuations modify the reaction free-energy surface by weakening the $\text{Ce}^{3+} - \text{H}$ bond of the MS intermediate and by promoting the barrierless H transfer into the O-H final state. We support this claim by performing a set of MD simulations that sample the stability of the $\text{Ce}^{3+} - \text{H}$ MS configuration as a function of increasing temperature. These show that the $\text{Ce}^{3+} - \text{H}$ group is stable only when the neighboring O atoms are close to their $T=0\text{K}$ equilibrium positions. By activating the atomic dynamics, the $\text{Ce}^{3+} - \text{H}$ configuration is stable along the whole MD run for temperatures up to $\approx 100\text{K}$, while it quickly decomposes and converts into a surface O-H group at $T \approx 150\text{K}$ and higher (see SI). According to this explanation, higher temperatures are not expected to further modify the free-energy surface because it is sufficient that the amplitude of the surface phonons is above a minimal threshold to facilitate the transfer of the H atom. Indeed, the free-energy reconstructed from the simulations at $T=150\text{ K}$ and $T=350\text{ K}$ display the same features (see SI).

Having demonstrated that entropic effects can guide the reaction mechanism, we now quantify them and show that they impact selectively only on the second part of the reaction mechanism (see yellow area in Fig.5). We denote as path 1 and path 2 the MEP obtained

from the T=0K CI-NEB calculations and from the T=350K reconstructed free-energy surface, respectively. The T=0K internal energy and T=350K reaction free energy along path 1 are displayed in Fig.5b). This comparison shows that the region of the free energy surface about path 1 is not primarily modified by entropic effects. The same analysis on the region of the free-energy surface about path 2 (Fig.5c) shows instead that there is a considerable difference between the internal energy (square symbols) and free energy (filled circles) profiles. To disentangle the entropic terms from the free energy we have calculated the internal energy along path 2 by selecting a set of configurations from the MD simulations having $[CV^{O-H}, CV^{H-H}]$ coordinates along path 2. Hence we run a structural minimization, keeping constant their $[CV^{O-H}, CV^{H-H}]$ coordinates. This provides the total energy profile at T=0K along path 2. The differences between the free energy and the internal energy along path 1 and 2 quantify the entropic terms TS in these regions of the reaction free energy. The TS terms are reported in Fig.5d). Despite the sizeable error-bars in taking the difference between the absolute values of the internal and free energies (leading sometimes to unphysical negative values), this analysis clearly shows that entropy affects the free-energy landscape selectively, only about the second part of the reaction path 2, which is related to the stability of the Ce^{3+} -H intermediate and to the barrierless H transfer to form surface OH groups.

The major effect of entropic terms is therefore to reduce the activation energy for H_2 dissociation by $\approx 26\%$, from 0.99 eV (value from static calculations T=0 K) to ≈ 0.73 eV. This activation barrier corresponds to the energy to break the H-H bond at the ceria surface, i.e. to the first part of the free-energy reaction path2, which is very well approximated by the T=0K calculations (Fig.5c). By inserting the results of the simulations into transition state theory and considering a prefactor of 10^{13} - 10^{14} Hz (the vibrational frequency of the H_2 molecule is 4395 cm^{-1} ,³³) an activation energy of 0.75 eV gives a rate of 10 s^{-1} at T=290-320 K, while the corresponding temperature obtained with the T=0 K barrier (0.99 eV) gives the same rate at 380-410 K. The difference in the predicted reaction barrier at T=0K and T=350K therefore yields a reduction in the activation energy of $\approx 100\text{K}$. Both values are much

lower than the experimental activation temperatures for the reduction of ceria powders by molecular hydrogen, 470 K.^{9,10} We remark the well-known problem of plain DFT functionals that systematically underestimate the transition-state barriers of chemical reactions.³⁴ The mean absolute deviation for a large set of reactions is as large as 0.6 eV for the local density approximation and 0.35 eV for the GGA-PBE functional.³⁴⁻³⁶ By taking into account this constant deviation to the calculated free-energy barriers, the predicted activation energy and temperature are 1.10 eV and 430-470 K, respectively, which are in reasonable agreement with the experimental values.

We also note that, in addition to the deviation due to the functional, a direct comparison with experiment should also consider quantum tunneling effects¹⁶ and non-local corrections,³⁷ which have been shown to affect the activation energy for hydrogen dissociation by as much as 0.3 eV. Including these correction into simulations sampling the minimum energy paths in the free energy remains a challenge to be addressed in the future.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have determined the reaction mechanism and thermodynamics of the H₂ dissociation at ceria surfaces by combining Car-Parrinello DFT+U molecular dynamics calculations with computational approach for the simulation of rare events. This approach allowed to include explicitly the effects of atomic thermal fluctuations into the calculations and to map the free energy hypersurface governing the hydroxylation and reduction of ceria surfaces.

The process proceeds along a complex pathway in which the molecular dissociation is accompanied by electron transfer to the support, and leads to surface reduction and hydroxylation. With respect to the minimum-energy path in the potential energy surface, our reaction free energy show that entropic effects i) reduce the activation energy by $\approx 25\%$ and ii) change the rate-limiting step from the migration of the H atom (at T=0 K) to the actual

H-H bond breaking (at finite T). The atomistic origins of these effects lie in the thermal fluctuation of the position of the surface O atoms, that is activated by temperature and that therefore plays a so-far unrecognized role in the hydroxylation and reduction of ceria surfaces.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge the FP7-NMP-2012 project chipCAT under Contract No. 310191 and the EU FP7 COST action CM104 for financial support, and the ISCRA initiative of CINECA for high performance computing resources.

Supporting Information Available

Details and results of the CI-NEB calculations at standard and higher accuracy. Results of the metadynamic simulations.

This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org/>.

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Graphical TOC Entry

